

Pant Dhan 4, Pant Dhan 10, and Pant Dhan 12) at two N fertility levels.

The experiment was conducted in the 1994 and 1995 wet seasons at Pantnagar, where the soil is a silt loam (Aquic Hapludoll) with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, 0.1 % total N, and CEC 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. N level (120 and 160 kg N ha⁻¹) was in the main plot and varieties (PRH-1, Jaya, Pant Dhan 4, Pant Dhan 10, and Pant Dhan 12) in the subplots. A single basal dose of 17.5 kg P ha⁻¹, 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹, and 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹ was uniformly applied in all plots. N was applied as per treatment in three splits: 1/2 as basal, 1/4 topdressed at active tillering, and 1/4 topdressed at panicle initiation. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted on 7 Jul in both years at 20- × 20-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings hill⁻¹.

Varieties did not respond differently to N. An additional dose of 40 kg N (bringing total N to 160 kg ha⁻¹) helped plants yield 7% more grain than at 120 kg N ha⁻¹ the recommended dose for high-yielding inbreds. The difference, however, was not significant (see table).

Hybrid rice PRH-1 yielded significantly more (17% in 1994 and 13% in 1995) than the best-performing inbreds: Jaya (12% less), Pant Dhan 4 (17% less), Pant Dhan 10 (19% less), and Pant Dhan 12 (15% less).

Based on these findings, suitable hybrids can produce 15-20% more than today's best inbred varieties in intensive input systems. ■

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.

FKR42 and FKR44: irrigated rice varieties released to farmers in Burkina Faso

M. Sie, Y. Sere, and A. Sanou, Institut d' études et de recherche agricoles (INERA), station de Farako-Bâ, 01 BP 910, Bobo-Dioulasso, 01 Burkina Faso, West Africa

Rice varieties IR64 and IR13240-108-2-2-3 were introduced into INERA's breeding program through collaboration with the International Network for

Genetic Evaluation of Rice and the West Africa Rice Development Association.

Both varieties proved promising in advanced yield trials in 1992-95 (see table). They also performed well in adaptive on-farm trials under farmers' cultural practices.

The varieties are early-maturing with long, slender grains and are suited for irrigated rice - rice double cropping. Both were released in 1995: IR64 as FKR42 (Farako-Bâ Riz) and IR13240-108-2-2-3 as FKR44. ■

Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) in irrigated rice variety trials^a at the INERA research stations in the Kou and Sourou valleys, Burkina Faso. 1992-95 wet (WS) and dry seasons (DS).

Variety	Kou Valley				Sourou Valley	
	1992 WS	1993 DS	1994 WS	1995 DS	1994 WS	1995 DS
IR64 (FKR42)	4.3	4.3	4.0	2.4	6.1	6.9
IR13240-108-2-2-3 (FKR44)	—	—	4.7	2.8	—	7.7
ITA123 (FKR28)	4.1	2.1	4.3	3.0	3.2	7.7
4456 (FKR16)	4.1	3.1	4.4	2.9	5.4	6.6

^aFertilizer rate = 88-69-42 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

Integrated germplasm improvement — upland

Evaluating local germplasm for the upland rice ecosystem in western Nepal

K. D. Joshi, Local Initiatives for Biodiversity, Research and Development, Pokhara, Nepal; B. R. Sthapit, Nepal Agriculture Research Council, Khumaltar, Nepal

Upland rice, locally known as *ghaiya dhan* in Nepal, is grown as the major crop in the *tars* (unirrigated ancient river fans), on terraced lands, and on hills where forests have recently been cleared. Most of the 126,000 ha (9% of the country's total rice area) under *ghaiya* is hilly. Resource-poor upland farmers from ethnic groups such as the Kumal, Derai, and Bote are the main growers of this rice.

Of the 42 rice varieties released in Nepal, only *Ghaiya 2* (MV10) is suitable for subtropical upland areas. Hill farmers, however, do not like it because it is

short and does not perform well under fertility.

Indigenous *ghaiya* varieties have not been properly studied or used in variety development programs that could benefit large farming communities.

Researchers at the Lumle Agricultural Research Center have done some preliminary work on evaluating local germplasm. They screened 53 *ghaiya* land races from Gorkha and Tanahun districts and evaluated them in replicated randomized complete block designs in a target environment (Chyanglitar, 400 m) for two seasons. The crop was broadcast and grown using farmers' practices, except for maintaining a row spacing of 15 cm between the entries. Farmers were involved in ranking the varieties at maturity. *Ghaiya* varieties that performed poorly during the first year were dropped. Only 24 varieties were tested during the second season.